

LIMIT STRAIN IN THE ELASTIC-PLASTIC ANALYSIS IN STEEL

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ABSTRACT

The elastic-plastic analysis design approach is a relatively new method gaining acceptance in engineering practice. This method simulates the relevant behavioral effects, eliminating the need for some of the prescriptive and restrictive design equations in current standards. It has provided accurate results across a range of cases. Currently, fractures are accounted for in design by using plastic strain limits. Plastic strains are influenced by various factors, including physical material, geometric properties, and analysis features such as element type, mesh density, and constitutive relations. This paper introduces the limit strain for different ratios of the diameter of holes to the width of a plate for specimens made of high-strength steel S700.

Keywords: Limit plastic strain, finite shell element, stress concentration, numerical model

1 INTRODUCTION

In structural engineering, there are so many cases where designing steel elements with concentrators is essential. This is particularly true with bolted connections or plates with mounting holes. In such sections, local stress peaks are formed at the edge of the concentrators, which can be several times greater than the value of nominal stress σ_n in the weakened section. The ratio between the maximum and nominal stress is called the stress concentration factor K_t . Then, the maximum stress σ_{max} can be obtained with the following function (1).

$$\sigma_{max} = K_t \sigma_n \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Stress concentration factor for an ended plate with hole (2).

According to Howland (2), the stress concentration factor K_t is associated with the ratio of the circular hole's radius a to the plate's width w (see Fig. 1) However, this approach only applies when using an elastic material model where stress and strain exhibit a linear relationship. It has limitations, such as significant underestimations when using weakened sections and significant deviations compared to experimental specimens. A more accurate material model is the elastic-plastic model, which has a different slope of the stress-strain curve after reaching the yield point. Figure 2 compares the stress and strain concentration factors of both material models (3).

Fig. 2. Comparison of concentration factors in elastic and elastic-plastic material models (3).

Each structural element has a maximum allowable load, beyond which the cross-section ceases to behave elastically. The limit can be measured by the design force, Criterion C1, or the maximum deformation/strain induced by the design force (4), Criterion C2. In the case of numerical finite element method calculations, the suitable limiting value is the plastic strain, especially for an elastic-plastic material model. Both criteria can be linked using the Neuber rule and the total strain energy density equivalence (3) (see Fig. 3).

$$(K_t \sigma_n) \epsilon_{22}^e = \sigma_{22}^a \epsilon_{22}^a \quad (2)$$

where σ_{22}^a , ϵ_{22}^a are the stress and the strain for the elastic-plastic material model, ϵ_{22}^e is the value of plastic strain for the elastic material model. The value of nominal stress depends on the force and the net cross-section area $\sigma_n = F/A_n$ and according to the provision of Eurocode EN1993-1-1(5), the limit load can be considered as the design plastic resistance with the following function:

$$F = N_{u,Rd} = (k/\gamma_{M2}) A_n f_u \quad (3)$$

where f_u is the ultimate strength and $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$, the partial factor for resistance of cross-sections in tension to fracture (5-6). Additionally, the correction factor k for the ultimate resistance of the net-cross section varies based on the quality of making hole's edge. The value of the correction factor is 1 for smooth holes and 0.9 for other cases (5-6).

Fig. 3. The total strain energies in the elastic and elastic-plastic material models (3).

The value of the plastic strain ε_{22}^a depends on the accuracy of the numerical solution. The mesh size is a crucial variable in this case and for shell solutions, mesh sizes $0.4t \times 0.4t$ and $1t \times 1t$ are recommended (7). This is because the same approach is followed to obtain maximum strains as the maximum stress range in the Hot-Spot stress method.

This work presents a numerical analysis of the limit values of plastic strains, criterion C2, for tension specimens of a plate with a hole made from high-strength steel S700.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Experiments were conducted on tension specimens made of high-strength steel S700 (8). Each sample had a hole at the center with a diameter d ranging from 8 to 40 mm. The plate width w was 80 mm. The hole-to-width ratios were $d/w = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$ a 0.5 , as shown in Figure 4. The thickness of the tested specimens was $t = 8$ mm. Two material models were used: a multilinear model in volume models for numerical validation (8), and a bilinear model in shell models. Figure 5 represents both material modes. The bilinear material model had parameters of yield strength f_y , Young's modulus E , and tangent modulus E_{tan} . The yield strength was assumed to be the stress at 0.2 % strain $f_y = 640$ MPa and Young's modulus was $E = 210$ GPa. Whereas the tangent modulus E_{tan} was solved as:

$$E_{tan} = (f_u - f_y)/(\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_y) = (867.5 - 640)/(0.09 - 0.002) = 2.55 \text{ GPa} \quad (4)$$

A numerical mesh was created using 20-node cubic elements for solid models and 4-node quadrilateral elements for shell models. All numerical solutions were prepared with the four mesh sizes - $2t \times 2t$, $1t \times 1t$, $0.5t \times 0.5t$ and $0.25t \times 0.25t$, as shown in Figure 6. To select the appropriate mesh size for the numerical solutions, the achieved deformations were validated against experimental values, see Fig. 7, and the maximum stresses in the elastic part were verified against analytical stresses calculated using equation (1) with stress concentration factor from Howland (2),

see Fig. 8. The most accurate solution was obtained with a mesh size of $0.5 t \times 0.5 t$ and it is considered for the further calculations.

Fig. 4. The geometries of the tested specimens (8).

Fig. 5. The material models used in finite element modeling.

The limit loads for the net cross-section in tension were calculated according to equation (3), and the plastic strains were determined using shell and solid models. Shell models were solved using the large deflection theory (LDT) and the small deflection theory (SDT).

Fig. 6. The mesh sizes of the solid and shell models with diameter of hole 6 mm:
 a) $2t \times 2t = 16 \times 16$ mm, b) $1t \times 1t = 8 \times 8$ mm,
 c) $0.5t \times 0.5t = 4 \times 4$ mm, d) $0.25t \times 0.25t = 2 \times 2$ mm.

The limit load is dependent on the material model. The solid model was calculated with a multilinear material model with a small difference between yield strength and ultimate strength of steel. The solid numerical solution was limiting values 1.1 % for $k = 0.9$ and 1.8 % for $k = 1$. Figure 9 depicts the plastic strains ε_{22}^a , which corresponds to the ratio of the hole diameter to the plate width d/w , and has minimum sensitivity with the dimension ratio. Similarly, shell models used a bilinear material model with a specified yield strength having a more significant difference with ultimate strength. The plastic limit values were 0.6 % for $k = 0.9$ and 4.8 % for $k = 1$. The latter value is highly sensitive to the ratio of the hole diameter to the plate width d/w , with smaller holes exhibiting higher limit values.

Fig. 7. Validation of the solid numerical model with diameter of hole 32 mm.

Fig. 8. Verification of the solid numerical model with diameter of hole 32 mm.

Fig. 9. Graphs of the plastic limits to ratio of the diameter of hole to the width of plate d/w .

3 SUMMARY

A study was conducted to determine the plastic strain limit in a plate made from high-strength steel S700 with a hole under tension. The experimental results of Hradil (8) were considered for the numerical analysis by creating solid and finite shell elements. The obtained results were as follows:

- The results showed that the most accurate solution was achieved with a mesh size of $0.5t \times 0.5t$.
- The limit value of plastic strain depends on the material model.
- The study also found that Criterion C2, with a correction factor $k = 0.9$ for shell models, is 0.6% and is not very sensitive to the hole size. At the same time, with a correction factor $k = 1$ for shell models, it is 4.8 % and is sensitive to the hole diameter ratio to the sheet width d/w .

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